

Cotton-wool-like borosilicate glass fibers for tissue regeneration: Preparation, characterization and in vitro bioactivity

Susanta Sengupta^{a,b}, Liliana Liverani^{b,c}, Dušan Galusek^{a,d}, Aldo R. Boccaccini^{b,*}

^a Centre for Functional and Surface Functionalized Glass, Alexander Dubcek University of Trenčín, Slovakia

^b Institute of Biomaterials, Department of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, Erlangen, Germany

^c DGS SpA, Rome, Italy

^d Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD and FChFT STU, FunGlass, Trenčín, Slovakia

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Bioactive glass
Electrospinning
Sol-gel

ABSTRACT

Borosilicate (60SiO₂-20CaO-16B₂O₃-4P₂O₅) glass fibers (BSGF) were fabricated by electrospinning in combination with sol-gel processing. BSGF were calcined at 600, 700 and 800 °C to remove the polymeric binder and optimize the formation of the inorganic phase. HCA (hydroxycarbonate apatite) was formed on BSGF within 24h of immersion in simulated body fluid (SBF), which was confirmed by XRD and FTIR analyses. In vitro cytotoxicity was measured with mouse osteoblast and fibroblast cell lines. WST-8 assay and fluorescence images confirmed the non-cytotoxic nature of the BSGF which did not induce any adverse effect on the cell activity.

1. Introduction

After their discovery in 1969, bioactive glasses (BGs) have been thoroughly investigated for tissue engineering applications while implants derived from BGs have been used for the repair and replacement of damaged bone tissue [1]. After the original silicate 45S5 BG (45SiO₂-24.5Na₂O-24.5CaO-6P₂O₅, in wt%), borate and borosilicate based BGs draw a great attention due to their higher degradation rate (in some compositions) and a better ability to form an apatite layer compared to silicate-based glass systems [2]. Moreover, B is an essential element and its release from BGs can facilitate several biological processes including new bone formation by triggering osteogenesis, neovascularization by angiogenesis along with antimicrobial activity [3,4]. BGs are conventionally used in form of particulates (solid or porous) or in bulk form or porous structures. On the other hand, research on BG fibers is an emerging field, in particular fiber structures with cotton-wool-like morphology that can be utilized as deformable or pliable 3D scaffolds or malleable wound dressings [5,6]. Current results indicate that bioactive glass wool could be beneficial as a dental bone graft substitute as well as wound dressing material for full thickness skin defects [5,7]. Traditional processing of BG fibers by melting technique involves high temperature processing and requires complex laboratory equipment [3]. Thus, BG fiber production by electrospinning combined with sol-gel processing of BG precursors could replace the conventional

fiber production process using less-complex equipment combined with room temperature processing. Preparation of silicate-based glass fibers with cotton-wool-like morphology obtained both with and without support of polymeric binders has been recently reported [5–9], including fiber mats based on borosilicate glass [10]. However, to the best of our knowledge, the preparation of electrospun cotton-wool-like BSGF has not been reported to date. In this study, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)-BG sol mixtures were employed to obtain BSGF. The calcination profile was optimized to tune the glass phase within the BSGF. In vitro bioactivity was determined in simulated body fluid (SBF) and cytotoxicity studies with the MC3T3-E1 and NIH3T3 cell lines were also carried out to preliminary assess BSGF cytocompatibility.

2. Materials and methods

Borosilicate glass sol (60SiO₂-20CaO-16B₂O₃-4P₂O₅) has been prepared by mixing the precursors in the following order. Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS, Sigma-Aldrich, ≥99%) was added to EtOH, then 0.1 (N) aq. HNO₃, calcium nitrate tetrahydrate [Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O, VWR, ≥98.5%], tributyl borate (TBB, Acros Organics, 98%), and triethyl phosphate (TEP, Sigma-Aldrich, ≥99%) were added in 1 h time intervals. Prior to electrospinning, the mixture was stirred for 24 h followed by 1 day ageing at room temperature (23–25 °C). Throughout the ageing process, the flask containing the sol remained sealed tightly with

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: aldo.boccaccini@fau.de (A.R. Boccaccini).

Fig. 1. SEM images of A) top surface and B) cross section of BSGF before (BS) and after calcination at various temperatures. C) XRD patterns and D) FTIR spectra of BSGF after calcination (CaP-calcium phosphate phase, β -CaP- β -calcium pyrophosphate).

a screw cap and further secured with parafilm to prevent solvent (ethanol) evaporation to the greatest extent possible. As the system was closed, the influence of possible relative humidity changes was considered to be negligible.

PVA (5 w/v %, M.W. \sim 72000 g/mol, Applichem Pan.) solution was prepared in hot water bath at 80 °C. Then, PVA and BG sol were mixed in a 1:1 (v/v) ratio. The PVA-BG mixture was transferred to a 3 mL syringe with needle tip (22G). The electrospinning process was performed with the help of a syringe pump (Starter Kit 40 KV Web, Linari Engineering). Electrospinning parameters were optimized and the voltage of 20 kV, collector-needle distance of 15 cm, and flow rate of 1 mL/h were applied in the process. Relative humidity (RH) of 35-37% and a temperature of 24.5 °C were maintained during the whole process. After electrospinning, BSGF were calcined at 600, 700 and 800 °C for 5h with a heating rate of 2 °C \cdot min $^{-1}$. The samples were denoted as BS600, BS700 and BS800, respectively.

The average fiber diameters were measured from SEM micrographs (Auriga, Zeiss, Germany) with the ImageJ software. Chemical environment of fibers with different functional groups was investigated by FTIR spectrophotometer (IRAffinity-1S, Shimadzu, Japan). The fibers (25 mg) were immersed in 50 mL of SBF for 1, 3 and 7 days to study acellular bioactivity following Kokubo's test [11]. XRD analysis (Rigaku, Mini-Flex 600, Japan) was performed to analyze the phase composition of the materials before and after immersion in SBF.

Preliminary indirect cell studies were performed with mouse pre-osteoblastic cell line MC3T3-E1 and embryonic fibroblast cell line NIH3T3 (ECACCS, Germany). Cells with the inoculum ratio of 10⁵ cells/mL were seeded and cultured with the filtered ionic extracts from BSGF in cell culture medium for 48 h. Cytocompatibility was determined by WST-8 assay (Sigma-Aldrich) along with fluorescence microscopy observations, as described elsewhere [12].

3. Results and discussion

The composition of the BSGF and the polymeric binder concentration were selected on the basis of preliminary trials. Higher concentrations of B₂O₃ (\geq 20 mol %) and PVA (\geq 10 w/v %) led to gelation of the sol and deformation of the fibers.

The samples were weighed before and after calcination and no significant change of weight was observed. The color of samples changed (Fig. S1) from grey to pale white and finally white after calcination at 600, 700 and 800 °C.

Under the optimized electrospinning conditions bead-free homogeneous fibers were formed, as confirmed by SEM examination (Fig. 1A). Increasing the calcination temperature, the average fiber diameter was reduced from $1.9 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{m}$ before calcination to 1.3 ± 0.2 , 1.2 ± 0.2 , and $1.0 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$, after calcination at the mentioned temperature. SEM images (Fig. 1B) of cross-sectional views of fibers showed their internal porous structure, which was present before calcination and was gradually reduced with increasing calcination temperature. The internal porous structure was formed as the result of solvent (H₂O, EtOH) evaporation during electrospinning.

XRD patterns (Fig. 1C) showed that increasing calcination temperature resulted in the formation of a crystalline phase. Amorphous BSGF were prepared at 600 °C, whereas crystalline phosphate phases such as calcium phosphate (JCPDS-01-072-7587) and β -calcium pyrophosphate (JCPDS-01-071-2123) were formed after calcination at 700 and 800 °C [13,14].

FTIR spectra (Fig. 1D) of BSGF revealed characteristic peaks of borosilicate glass. The bands at 1300-1460 and 675 cm $^{-1}$ were attributed to B-O symmetric stretching and bending mode of BO₃. The peak at 920 cm $^{-1}$ was assigned to B-O stretching mode of BO₄ and Si-O-B symmetric stretching frequency. The broad peak at 980-1220 cm $^{-1}$ was associated

Fig. 2. A) Low and B) high magnification SEM images, C) XRD patterns, and D) FTIR spectra of BSGF (BS600) after (1, 3 and 7 days) immersion in SBF.

with asymmetric stretching mode of Si-O-Si along with the tri-, tetra-, and di-borate groups belonging to BO_3 and BO_4 units [15,16]. The peaks at 457 and 802 cm^{-1} were ascribed to bending and symmetric stretching vibration of Si-O-Si and O-Si-O groups, respectively [16]. In BS600, the amorphous nature of the phases containing PO_4^{3-} groups was documented by a broad P-O resonance at 550-610 cm^{-1} , which splits into two peaks at 565 and 607 cm^{-1} resembling the crystalline phosphate phase present in BS700 and BS800 after calcination [13].

A study in SBF was carried out with the sample BS600 because no crystalline phases were detected in the fibers by XRD after the calcination and apatite formation can be thus easily discerned. It was anticipated that the fibers would be more bendable than the crystallized fibers, although they were not tested in terms of their flexibility. SEM images (Fig. 2A and B) show biom mineralization of BSGF. Crystalline apatite-like structures were formed on the surface of the fibers which became thicker after the immersion in SBF [2,5]. XRD (Fig. 2C) and FTIR results (Fig. 2D) provided an additional evidence of apatite phase formation. The diffraction lines at $2\theta \sim 26^\circ$ and 32° after 1 day of immersion in SBF and additional diffraction lines at 45° and 56° after 3 and 7 days can be attributed to the formation of HCA. FTIR bands at 567, 603 and 1030 cm^{-1} were ascribed to bending and stretching modes of PO_4^{3-} confirming crystallization of a phosphate phase already after 1 day of immersion in SBF. The resonance frequency of CO_3^{2-} at 875 cm^{-1} was also ascribed to formation of HCA after 3 and 7 days of SBF immersion [2].

Cell viability tests revealed that ionic extracts from BSGF (BS600) were not cytotoxic to MC3T3-E1 cells (values higher than 90%

compared with the positive control, Fig. 3). However, ionic extracts with the concentrations of 0.5 and 0.1% (w/v) were cytotoxic (values similar to the negative control) for the NIH3T3 cell line. For the ionic extract diluted to 0.05% the cell viability reached 60% of the positive control. Fluorescence images supported the results of WST-8 assay (Fig. 3).

4. Conclusions

BSGF with cotton wool-like morphology were prepared by electrospinning of PVA-sol mixture and their calcination profile was optimized. Calcination at $T > 600^\circ\text{C}$ led to partial crystallization of the glass fibers. In vitro bioactivity in SBF and cytocompatibility studies showed that BSGF (calcined at 600°C) could be useful candidates for bone tissue regeneration along with wound healing applications, as they show mineralization ability and, depending on concentration, their dissolution products are not cytotoxic. The effect of boron on the possible angiogenic properties of the fibers will be the main subject of future investigations.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. 3. Relative cell viability measured from WST-8 assay and fluorescence images (red-cytoskeleton, blue-nuclei) of MC3T3-E1 and NIH3T3 cells cultured with ionic extracts from BS600. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Acknowledgment

The authors are grateful to JECS Trust for funding the visit of Susanta Sengupta to the Institute of Biomaterials, FAU (grant agreement No. 2021266). The research was co-funded by project FunGlass, European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (GA No. 739566).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceram.2023.100419>.

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